

EFFECT OF EXTENSIVE AND INTENSIVE INTERVAL TRAINING ON LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG SCHOOL BOYS

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Abstract:

To facilitate the study, forty five school boys from Tirunelveli were selected as subjects at random and their age was between 14 to 16 years. They were divided into three equal groups namely, 'Extensive Training Group' (E.T.G), 'Intensive Training Group' (I.T.G), and 'Control Group' (C.G). The 'Extensive Training Group' was subjected to extensive interval training; the 'Intensive Training Group' was exposed to intensive interval training while 'Control Group' was left on their own. For Extensive Interval Training Group 60 to 80 percent of intensity was given for five days in a week for eight weeks. The F- ratio for the adjusted post-test means was computed by analysis of covariance. Study proved that the Extensive Training Group has definite effect on the increase of Life Satisfaction than Intensive Training Group.

Key Words: Interval Training, Life Satisfaction, School Boys.

Introduction:

The modern trends in sports and games reflect advanced technological developments and scientific methods of training and athletics. As such, the training sessions should aim at the purpose and have a pragmatic approach to improve the performance of the individuals and the teams through systematic and scientifically constructed training methods. Interval training is broadly defined as repetitions of high-speed/intensity work followed by periods of rest or low activity. In the present study, the investigator has been quite enthusiastic to know the changes brought about by two different trainings namely extensive training group and intensive training group on Life Satisfaction.

If proved favourable, the study would enable physical educationists to adhere to these trainings to lead them towards the development of physical fitness and thereby towards the better performance in sports without encountering the harmful side of misusing. The subjects were measured for Life Satisfaction before training as well as immediately after eight weeks training. The significance of the difference among the means of control group, extensive training and intensive training groups pre-test and post-test were determined by F-ratio through the analysis of co-variance. The F-ratio for the adjusted posttest means was computed by analysis of co-variance. The levels of significance were set at .05 levels. In addition, the significance of the difference between paired adjusted final means computed by means of Scheffe's post-hoc test method.

Methodology:

To facilitate the study, forty five school boys from Tirunelveli were selected as subjects at random and their age was between 14 to 16 years. They were divided into three equal groups namely, 'Extensive Training Group' (E.T.G), 'Intensive Training Group' (I.T.G), and 'Control Group' (C.G). The 'Extensive Training Group' was subjected to extensive interval training; the 'Intensive Training Group' was exposed to intensive interval training while 'Control Group' was left on their own.

For Extensive Interval Training Group 60 to 80 percent of intensity was given for five days in a week for eight weeks. For Intensive Interval Training Group 80 to 90 percent intensity was given for five days in a week for eight weeks. The running distance was classified as 100 meters, 200 meters, 300 meters, and 400 meters. The running distance was varied every day, first day 100 meters training, second day 200 meters training third day 300 meters training, fourth day 400 meters training, fifth day again 100 meters training and so on, and control group was left on their own. The pre-test was taken from the subjects two days before administering the extensive interval training and intensive interval training.

The subjects were involved with their respective extensive training group and intensive training group for a period of eight weeks under the personal supervision of the researchers. At the end of eight weeks, the post-test was taken. The significant difference between the means of Extensive Training Group, Intensive Training, and Control Group for the pre - test and post - test scores were determined by analysis of variance. The F- ratio for the adjusted post-test means was computed by analysis of covariance. The level of significance was fixed at 0.05 levels.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Analysis of Covariance of Pre - Test, Post-Test on Life Satisfaction of Extensive Training Group, Intensive Training Group and Control Group

Test	Exp. Gr. I	Exp. Gr. II	Cont. Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Means Squares	Obtained F Value
Pre Test	18.66	19.53	17.33	between	36.84	2	18.422	2.14
				within	362.40	42	8.63	
Post Test	25.33	24.93	16.87	between	684.58	2	342.29	45.21*
				within	318.00	42	7.57	
Adjusted Post Test	25.32	24.85	16.96	between	611.81	2	305.90	39.75*
				within	315.539	41	7.70	
Mean Gain	6.66	5.40	0.47					

* Significant, NS - Not Significant

Table 2: Ordered Adjusted Life Satisfaction Means, Differences between Means and Scheffe's Post-Hoc Test F-Ratio of Extensive training Group, Intensive Training Group and Control Group Scheffe's Post-Hoc Test for Life Satisfaction

Exp. Gr. I	Exp. Gr. II	Control Group	Mean Difference	C.I
25.32	24.85	-	0.47*	0.32
25.32	-	16.96	8.36*	0.32
-	24.85	16.96	7.89*	0.32

* Significant

Results of Life Satisfaction:

The analysis of covariance of Life Satisfaction data between pre-test and post-test of the three groups have been presented in Table I. The data pertaining to the pre and post-test results of Life Satisfaction were presented in Gram per cent. Table I shows the analysis of covariance of Life Satisfaction. The pre-test means of extensive training group, intensive training group and control group were 18.66, 19.53, and 17.33 respectively. Since the obtained F-ratio of 2.14 is lower than the table F-ratio of 6.46 the pre-test means were not significant at 0.05 level of confidence with the degrees of freedom 2 and 42. The posttest means of extensive training group, intensive training group and control group were 25.33, 24.93, and 16.87 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 45.21 is seen to be higher than the table F-ratio of 3.22. Hence, the differences among the post-test means were significant at 0.05 level of confidence with degrees of freedom 2 and 42.

The adjusted post-test means of extensive training group, intensive training group and control group were 25.32, 24.85, and 16.96 respectively. Since the obtained F-ratio of 39.75 is higher than the table F-ratio of 3.23 the adjusted post-test mean difference amount the three groups were significant at 0.05 level of confidence with the degrees of freedom 2 and 41. Scheffe's post-hoc test was resorted-to, to find out the significance of ordered adjusted final means difference among the groups. Table II shows the Scheffe's post-hoc test results. The ordered adjusted Life Satisfaction means, differences between means and scheffe's post-hoc test F-ratio of Extensive Training Group and Intensive Training Group and Control Group were tested for significance against scheffe's post-hoc test F-ratio. The mean difference between Extensive Training Group and Intensive Training Group, Extensive Training Group and Control group, and Intensive Training Group and Control Group were 0.47, 8.36, and 7.89 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 2.14, 45.21, and 39.75 was seen to be higher than the table F-ratio of 3.23. Hence, the above comparisons were significant at 0.05 level.

Discussion on Findings of Life Satisfaction:

The result indicated that the Extensive Training Group and Intensive Training Group had significantly increased in Life Satisfaction in terms of mean gain when compared with Control Group among school boys. In particular, the Extensive Training Group had significant improvement in Life Satisfaction than Intensive Training Group. Finally, the findings of the present study proved that the Extensive Training Group has definite effect on the increase of Life Satisfaction than Intensive Training Group.

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